

PECULIARITIES OF THE USE OF NUMBERS IN THE
LANGUAGE OF QAZI MAWLİK'S WORKS**Orinbaeva Jupargul**independent researcher at the Department of Karakalpak Linguistics
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ABSTRACT

The article examines the features of numbers and their use in the works of the 20th-century Karakalpak poet Qazi Mawlik.

When studying the history of the development of the literary languages of Turkic-speaking peoples, it is important to consider the works of literary masters, who occupy a special place in the cultural life of their people, in a linguistic context. After all, literary language is a form of the national language, cultivated and creatively enriched by literary masters. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate literary language as a mature, elevated form of national oral culture. The literary master directs and develops this creative process. Among poets who lived and wrote at the beginning of the 20th century, the works of Kazi Mavlik Bekmukhammad oglu occupy a special place due to their linguistic features. The artistic quality of Kazi Mavlik's works was studied in a separate monographic section by literary scholar B. Davletov [1].

The language of the poet's works stands out among the works of his contemporaries with its unique features. That is, the master of words created his works mainly on the model of written literary traditions common to all Turkic peoples of that time. Kazi Mavlik stands out among the works of Karakalpak poets of the 20th century, such as Sariboy, Gulmurat Kurbanli oglu and others, for his unique features of word formation, methods of artistic expression and, especially, the peculiarities of his language. It often contains phonetic-morphological, lexical-semantic features characteristic of the ancient Turkic literary language. Therefore, it is necessary to study the language of the poet's works from different angles. In this article, we will look at the features of using numeric words in the language of the poet's works.

Although there are meaningful forms of numbers in the language of Kazi Mavlik's works, as well as in the modern Karakalpak language, not all of them are often found in the poet's works.

Countable numbers. Numbers have a simple and composite structure. Numbers in the singular are used in the following forms:

A number is a group of words denoting the meaning of an abstract number or the quantity, volume, or order of an object. Using the number "one" is very effective.

Mısalı:

Bir kórgende bilir yaqshı-yamannı («Aqlım hayrandur»),

Bir bayaz aytayın desem shul yara («Aqlım hayrandur»),

Bir barna periyzat güller qırmanı («Yadıma túshti»),

Bir mini yoq barlıq aǵza táninde («Ne sózdur»),

Bir ayra tushib pántqumar aldım («Giripdar emdi»).

In the poet's works, the words "yakka" were used in the meaning of the number "bir", "ikki" in the meaning of the number "ekki", "juft" in the meaning of the number "two". For example:

Periyzatlar ishra *ekke* bir ózi («Aqlım hayrandur»),

Álemni shad etseń *jekke* bir óziń («Ol nege dárkar»),

Shahri Shımbay ishre *ekke* bir ózi («Ne sózdur»),

Siynasidan bir *yup* almanı úzar («Shımbay bayazı»).

In the poet's work, there are cases of using the phenomenon of gemination in the numbers two, seven, eight, nine, fifty. For example:

Boynı ikki gezdur, beli bir qushaq.

Eki elli bilán, yuqsa yúz bilán.

Sakkiz háripten piter ismi-sháripi.

Hár jagında sakkiz burım shashları.

In the poet's works, the phenomenon of epenthesis is also found, that is, the addition of the sound t, in the structure of the number 60. For example:

Raxatidur altmısh etti mıń ádet (Qazı Máwdud penen Safura qız aytısı).

In the poet's works, the number "eliw" (fifty) was used more often than the word "elli". The use of the numeral "ellik" in the form of "elli" is typical for Azerbaijani, Turkish and other Turkic languages of the Oghuz group [2.77]. For example:

Yuzde elli beshmıń saatǵa tolur (Qazı Máwdud penen Safura qız aytısı),

Eki elli bilán, yuqsa yúz bilán («Periyzat»).

In the Turkic language, the word "tuman" was used to refer to a very large number with the number one "thousand" attached in front of it. For example:

Mıń tumenge arzan altın basları («Megzettim»).

The number *bes* (five) in the form of "besh" was also often used. For example:

Altı yılını *besh waq* namaz bayanı (Qazı Máwdud penen Safura qız aytısı).

Since numerals indicate the quantity, the exact quantity of the subject, the noun used with them usually does not take the plural affix. However, in the works of Qazi Mawlik, there is a fact of joining plural affixes:

On jeti gez atları bar Shımbaydıń. («Shımbay bayazı»),

Hár jagında *sákkiz* burım shashları («Megzettim»),

Hár tárepte *on tórt* órim shashlarıń («Megzettim»).

Composite numerals consisting of several digits are also often found in the poet's works.

For example:

Yane besh yuz saksen miñni bir sanap..,

Toquz yuzde etmish sakkizge sánád (Qazı Máwdud penen Safura qız aytısı).

Numbers. The numeral of the series is not found in the poet's works, but the words of Arabic origin *áwel, áwwel* were used in the meaning of the numeral of the *first* row:

Áwelden bilmedim ańlap ózimni («Nedur gúnayım»).

Quantitative numerals. In the poet's work, approximate numerals are formed by combining two quantitative numerals. For example:

Mágar on tórt-on besh anıq yashları («Megzettim»),

Áyne shağı on tórt-on bes jasında («Shımbay bayazı»),

Bir-eki nusqada atıñni kórdim..,

Eki júz on tórt miñ yaki yuz dana (Qazı Máwdud penen Safura qız aytısı).

Thus, the numerals used in the language of Kazi Mavlik's works basically correspond to the numerals of the modern Karakalpak language. At the same time, there are peculiarities in the sound structure of some affixes that form groups of numerals in relation to our modern language. As a result, several types of numerals with phonetic and morphological features were used in the poet's language

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